

Design and Analysis of Composite Multilayer Antenna for the Structural Surface Application

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ABSTRACT

The present study aims to design a multilayer microstrip antenna with composite sandwich construction and investigate structural behavior of this multilayer structure for the next generation of structural surface technology. Surface antenna structure was designed with composite laminates, nomex honeycomb cores and constituent materials considered electrical properties. This structure had the good structural rigidity and the electrical performance. For the satellite communication, antenna elements were designed at a resonant frequency of 12.5 GHz and inserted into structural layers. Finally antenna was fabricated with 16×8 array for high gain, wide bandwidth and high polarization. From electrical measurements, it was shown that antenna performances were in good agreement with design requirements. The flexural behavior of surface antenna structure was experimentally determined in the condition of cyclic 4-point bending. The fatigue life curve of surface antenna structure was obtained. Experimental results were compared with single load level fatigue life prediction equations.

Keywords: Microstrip Antenna, Surface Antenna Structure, Sandwich Structure, Composite, Nomex Honeycomb, Bending Fatigue

1. INTRODUCTION

In the communication areas of vehicle, antenna roles are focused as main factor that confines ability and function of satellite communication and mobile communication. In implementing these services via satellite for vehicles especially, antenna will be one of the most important key technologies. That antennas are located on surface of the structure needs large space, and is large path-loss and junction-loss. Because of these negative effects, Structures Division of the Air Force's Wright Laboratory is sponsoring the development and demonstration of CLAS [1]. This program is called "Smart-Skin Structure Technology Demonstration (S³TD)" [2]. The program opted for a multi-arm spiral antenna embedded in a CLAS fuselage panel. The final demonstration article was a structurally effective 36×36 inch curved multifunction antenna component panel that withstood running loads of 4,000 pounds per inch. The objective of this work was to design a microstrip antenna for satellite communication application with composite sandwich construction and investigate fatigue behavior of this antenna that was asymmetric sandwich structure. This term, Surface Antenna Structure (SAS), indicates that structural surface becomes antenna. It was developed using simpler design procedures than CLAS. The basic structure is a composite sandwich that provides good structural conditions and space needed for the antenna to function properly. The structural stability including fatigue behavior and the fatigue life of SAS will be estimated and predicted through 4-point fatigue bending test.

2. DESIGN OF SURFACE-ANTENNA-STRUCTURE (SAS)

A microstrip antenna has significant advantages in size, ease of fabrication and compatibility with printed circuits but also defects such as narrow bandwidth and low efficiency. To overcome these

problems a new concept, SSFIP (strip-slot-foam-inverted patch) antenna, has been developed [3,4]. SAS adapted SSFIP concepts consists of two composite laminates, two honeycomb cores, two conducting materials (patch, feed line), and one 2024 T3 aluminum shielding plane.

The SAS of this study used commercial satellite communication requirements. The operation frequency has from 12.25 to 12.75 GHz. The antenna bandwidth should generally be about 50–100 MHz at the 1.5:1 VSWR level. The polarization used linear polarization. The beamwidth was required to be 5° in elevation and azimuth plane, and side-lobes level (SLL) must be reduced to -16 dB.

We designed single antenna element which resonates at 12.5 GHz frequency and is 8.22 mm square rectangular patch. The slot took the shape of ‘H’, so as to improve the coupling between feed and slot without widening the slot size. The characteristic impedance of feed line uses 100Ω. Fig. 1 shows single antenna element.

Fig. 1 Single Antenna Element

Fig. 2 Design of Feed Network of the Whole 16 x 8 Array Antenna

SSFIP single element was adapted to full array antenna. 8 sub-arrays, which have 16×1 single elements, were integrated linearly at 0.7λ intervals between each element to remove grating lobe. The feed network of array antennas was designed in a series/parallel form so as to reduce coupling between the sub-arrays. It consisted of a 3 dB tapered feed network at which the current decreases by 3 dB from the center, to give a beamwidth 5° in azimuth and elevation. It provided a SLL not exceeding -16 dB. Fig. 2 shows the whole 16×8 array antenna whose geometry dimension is 300×200×22.1 mm.

3. FABRICATION AND ANTENNA PERFORMANCE

3.1. Material Selection and Fabrication

Selecting SAS materials, electrical performance and mechanical efficiency must be considered. The substrate was a woven glass/hydrocarbon laminate (RO4003, Rogers corp.) with dielectric constant 3.38 and thickness 0.5 mm. Nomex honeycomb (HRH-10-1/8-5, Hexcel corp.) was used as a core material. Nomex honeycombs of thickness 2.54 and 19.05 mm were used for the upper and lower core to achieve good electrical and mechanical performances. For the shielding plane, 2024 T3 aluminum 0.5 mm thick was used to provide structural support as well as removing back radiation.

Fig. 3 Appearance of Fabricated Layers and Assembly

Manufacture of SAS was a sequential process. First, the top sheet with the radiating patch was etched. Then the middle sheet for the slot on the ground plane and feedline was etched. The honeycomb cores and each layer must be aligned before making permanent bonding. The layers were bonded to the top and bottom of the honeycomb cores with epoxy film adhesive (AF126, 3M corp.). The assembly was then cured under pressure in an autoclave. The result was a 300×200×22.1 mm flat antenna panel. Fig. 3 shows the appearance of each layer and the final assembly.

3.2. Antenna Performance

The Antenna performances of SAS were obtained by measuring return loss (RL) and radiation pattern which were shown in Fig. 4~6. The RL value of approximately -45 dB at 12.1 GHz was observed. This result was better than simulation result (-37 dB), but resonant frequency was shifted from 12.5 to 12.1 because of using feedline of a series/parallel form. A bandwidth of 800 MHz at VSWR of 1.5 was measured. The -3 dB beamwidths were less than 5° at both the azimuth and the elevation, and SLLs were -22 dB at azimuth and -17 dB at elevation. These results showed good agreement with satellite communication antenna requirements.

Fig. 4. Measured Return Loss

Fig. 5 Beam Patterns (Azimuth Plane)

Fig. 6 Beam Patterns (Elevation Plane)

4. STRUCTURAL EXPERIMENTS

4.1. Preparation of Specimens

SAS specimens were prepared from a woven glass/hydrocarbon laminate (RO4003, Rogers corp.), 2024 T3 aluminum and two honeycomb cores. The assembly was cured under pressure in an autoclave. Properties of the materials used were set out in Table 1. Dimension of beam specimen is 300×30×22.1 mm. Fig. 7 shows test specimen.

4.2. Experimental Procedure

The static 4-point bending test in accordance with ASTM C 393-62 [5] and 4-point bending fatigue test were performed using the MTS 810 material testing system. The specimens were supported by a quarter point-loading jig. Static tests were performed under displacement-control at a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min until failure. The fatigue tests were performed under load-control using a sinusoidal wave form applied at a frequency of 1 Hz, and carried out at limit for 10^6 cycles. Failure criterion for fatigue test was chosen to maximum deflection obtained from static tests. Applied load levels were determined 0.9-0.5 load levels of static load.

Table 1 Mechanical Properties of Constituent Materials

Property	Woven Glass/Hydrocarbon	2024 Al T3
Elastic modulus (GPa)	26	72
Tensile strength (MPa)	141	482
Property	Nomex honeycomb (HRH-10-1/8-5)	
Density (kg/m ³)	80.1	
Compressive strength (MPa)	4.83	
L-shear strength (MPa)	2.24	
W-shear strength (MPa)	1.21	

Test Specimen 30(mm) x 3(mm)

Fig. 7 Configurations of Specimens

Fig. 8 Static Flexural Behaviors of SAS

4.3 Results and Discussion

Fig. 8 shows displacement-load curve (D-L Curve) of static tests. As a whole D-L Curve was divided three blocks of A, B, and C, since SAS was consisted of elements of sandwich structure. Details of damage development were as follows.

1. A block: deflection propagates linearly through entire specimen. Then at discontinuous point between 'A' block and 'B' block, the failure of first laminate (face sheet) initiates.
2. B block: after first laminate crushing, deflection propagates linearly. At discontinuous point between 'A' block and 'B' block, first honeycomb is loaded of compression, and second laminate is failed.
3. C block: after deflection propagates entirely, finally SAS come to perfectly failure.

The face crushing and core wrinkling were observed in all specimens, because of due to an asymmetry between the top and bottom faces. The shielding plane on the bottom was stiffer than the top face-sheet and supported the in-plane tensile load until core failure occurred. At the final failure, bending load of SAS was 2.45 kN, and displacement was 5 mm. Flexure behavior of SAS was followed mode B (Core Shear) of Ashby [6] model.

During cyclic loading, the resultant displacement at the load level 0.85 is shown in Fig. 9. This result shows continual increase of resultant displacement with number of cycles. It suggests that SAS might undergo continual degradation from the early stage of loading till failure. It was found that displacements increase faster at higher load than at lower load. Both the resultant and permanent displacements increase rate, $d(\text{displacement})/dn$, increased drastically during final few cycles. Also the hysteresis loop energy increased fast during the final stage. The damage procedure of fatigue test was the same as static tests. After failure, Resultant displacements of SAS were 5.42 mm that is

longer than 5 mm of static test. This result conform that, Hwang's failure criterion [7-9], the failure of composites under fatigue loading occurs when the fatigue resultant displacement reaches a constant number times of the static ultimate displacement. Fig. 10 shows the log scale relation of load levels (ratio of applied load and bending load) and fatigue cycles. The load levels were between 0.9 and 0.5, and the numbers of tests specimens were 3 at each load levels. The test results explained that fatigue life of SAS was 0.75 load level (1.875 kN), and displacement was 5.42 mm, when fatigue limit is 10^6 cycles. The relations of resultant displacements and fatigue cycles were shown in Fig. 11. The resultant displacements of 0.61 and 0.5 load levels did not reach to, 5.42 mm, fatigue displacements, and others did, when occurring failure. The resultant displacements slowly increased at first, then increased drastically at final a few cycles. The fatigue test results give that SAS can support external loads as a structural surface with excellent antenna performance.

Fig. 9 Cyclic Load-Displacement of SAS

Fig.10 Fatigue Life Data

Fig.11 Resultant Disp. versus Cycles

Fig. 12 Fatigue Life Prediction Curve

Using fatigue test results, SFLPEs and experimental data were compared. SFLPEs to compare were Hwang's Equation [7-9], Basquin's Relation and S-N Curve.

$$\text{Hwang's Equation: } N = \exp[M(j^B - q^B)], \quad (1)$$

$$\text{Basquin's Relation: } L_a = l(2N)^b, \quad (2)$$

$$\text{S-N Curve: } q = k \log N + d, \quad (3)$$

where N is the fatigue life, L_a is the applied load, q is the applied load level, and k , d , l , and b are material constants. Using commercial engineering software Matlab 6.5, parameters were obtained. Details of SFLPEs were as follows.

$$\text{Hwang's Equation: } N = \left[\frac{0.542^{0.01315}}{0.01} (0.9225^{0.01315} - q^{0.01315}) \right]^{1/0.0157} \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Basquin's Relation: } L_a = 0.9368(2N)^{-0.01366} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{S-N Curve: } q = -0.02649 \log N + 0.9253 \quad (6)$$

The test results were plotted 3 data at each load levels. Fig. 12 shows that experimental results were compared with single load level fatigue life prediction equations and in good agreement.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The surface antenna structure (SAS) was designed, fabricated, and measured. The antenna

elements inserted were designed for requirements of satellite communication. The fabricated array antenna was a 300×200×22.1 mm flat antenna structure. The antenna performances were in good agreement with design requirements. The flexure behaviors of cyclic loading were obtained through 4-point bending fatigue test. The test results were compared with SFLPEs and in good agreement.

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